

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Project Number: 823782

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 40 months

Deliverable 4.11 Report on the experience with the automatic verification programme in SHARE wave 9

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/12/2021 (M36)
Actual Submission Date	15/10/2021 (M34)
Work Package	WP4 - Innovations in Data Production
Task	Task 4.3 Applying Computer Assisted Translation in Social Surveys
Type	Report
Approval Status	Waiting EC approval
Version	V3.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.21

Abstract:

This report describes the innovative steps in the translation procedures during the development of national versions of the SHARE questionnaire. The verification activity has been improved adding verification tools to the standard procedures. The outcome of making use of sanity checks and of an Automated Verification Tool (AVT) has been measured and analysed. The results of the verification exercise show efficiency gains in terms of time and effort with respect to the standard procedures, gains that are mainly driven by the sanity checks.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
1.0	31/07/2021	First version	Yuri Pettinicchi
1.1	27/08/2021	Review	Sebastiaan Pennings
2.0	03/09/2021	Version incorporating reviews	Yuri Pettinicchi
2.1	27/08/2021	Review	Diana Zavala-Rojas, Carsten Theil, Martina Drascic Capar
3.0	15/10/2021	Final Version	Yuri Pettinicchi

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
SHARE-ERIC	Yuri Pettinicchi	pettinicchi@mea.mpisoc.mpg.de
SHARE-ERIC	Yichen Liu	yichenliu329@gmail.com

Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable D4.11 of the Horizon2020 project “Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud”). It reports on the experience with the automatic verification checks implemented during the development phase of the questionnaire for SHARE wave 9. It describes the outcomes of the exercise, and it points out the critical issues to be addressed for further development.

The report starts with the motivation of the innovation and provides the context where the innovation takes place. The complexity of translating source text with programming syntax makes the task of the translators more difficult and affects the quality of the translations.

The section “Verification Tools” describes the tools developed, their technical implementation and the design of the innovative procedure. Two types of verification tool have been developed. The sanity check for the translations and the Automated Verification Tool (AVT). The former type consists of the empty text field check, the missing identification number check, the missing technical text check and the fill usage check. The latter one, the AVT, is able to compare the source and the target text and to assign a translation score to the text using the predictions made by a model.

The section “SHARE Exercise” lists the critical issues identified during the implementation phase. The sanity checks and the AVT worked technically fine. The procedure was easily understood by the translators and smoothly implemented. The performance mainly depends on the model trained.

The section “Results” summarizes the outcomes and the lesson learnt from the verification exercise. From the verification exercise, the SHARE team learnt that the innovation described makes the process more efficient in terms of effort and time. Sanity checks reduce the number of iterations in generating the national versions of the questionnaire tool. The preliminary results from the Automated Verification tool (AVT) provided mixed evidence about its contribution in improving the efficiency of the verification.

The final section concludes and mentions the direction for future steps. A way to improve the tool is to retrain the model with better training corpora. The training of bilingual phrase embeddings model could also improve the performance of the tool.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

TMT	Translation Management Tool
AVT	Automated Verification Tool
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (http://www.share-project.org)
ESS	European Social Survey (https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org)
EVS	European Values Study (https://europeanvaluesstudy.eu)
MCSQ	The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires
CATI	Computer Assisted Telephone Interview

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
2. Verification tools.....	8
2.1. Sanity checks	8
2.2. Automated Verification Tool (AVT).....	11
3. SHARE Exercise.....	12
3.1. The questionnaire.....	12
3.2. Workflow	13
4. Results	15
5. Conclusion	20
6. References	21

1. Introduction

SSHOC task 4.3 applies Computer Assisted Translation tools in Social Surveys with the aim of providing extra tools to the translators. Improving the working environment of the translators is one of the many solutions that social survey projects (e.g., SHARE, ESS, EVS) are pursuing. The working environment is usually chosen by a project leader, and it is constrained by the features of technology (i.e., selected software or web platform) used to manage the translation process.

The main task of the translators is to provide high quality translations of the text in the source language (the source text). When the source text is made available as plain text (e.g., a chapter of a book, an article in a newspaper) in a text editor, the translators focus on the content and, accounting for their expertise and the difficulty of the text, are able to deliver the translations in the target language (the target text), without further effort.

Survey projects work differently and usually do not provide source text as plain - unformatted - text. The source text is made available using a web platform that displays the texts, instructions for the translators and an editable text field for the translations, as any text editor does. The web platform is instrumental to the translation of special source text that needs to integrate programming syntax. The syntax accommodates the dynamically displaying of text (e.g., gender specific words) that needs to fit the characteristics of its audience (e.g., a question asked to a woman or to a man). Therefore, the extra layer of complexity of translating source text with programming syntax makes the task of the translators more difficult and affects the quality of the translations.

SHARE uses a questionnaire tool where the source questionnaire is embedded and enhanced with programming syntax. The questionnaire tool is able to display one question at the time in front of the interviewer, to manage the routing of the interview, and to record the answers of the respondent. Once the questionnaire tool is ready in the source language, the following steps are the replacement of the source language with the target language and the adjustment of the programming syntax in order to function correctly also for the target language.

SHARE uses the Translation Management Tool (TMT), a web-platform developed by CentERdata, to manage the translation process of the source questionnaire in 39 country-specific languages.¹ The TMT is able to handle plain text with programming syntax. However, the SHARE translators need to integrate the programming syntax in their translations and only the testers of the national version of the questionnaire tool are able to verify the correct functioning of the programming syntax. Multiple iterations are usually needed before the project manager is able to send the national version of the

¹ For more details, please check Martens (2017) and info sheet https://seriss.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/SERISS-Info-sheet_TMT.pdf

questionnaire tool to the Survey Agency. SHARE generates between two and five national versions per country involving translators, software developers, and testers.

The main concern for translation managers is to avoid mistakes that translators make when they operate in this special working environment. The standard expertise of the translators has little use in avoiding these types of mistakes. Gaining experience or training in a similar working environment could help but will not eliminate the risk of the need to regenerate another version of the questionnaire tool. In addition, the risk grows larger the more complex the programming syntax is, the higher the volume of source text is and the lesser the time available for the task is.

Within the SSHOC project, SHARE innovates the translation procedure with the aim of reducing the workload needed in generating new versions of the national questionnaire tools. The actions take place during the verification of the translations, right after the SHARE translators have provided the questionnaire in the target language and before the new version of the questionnaire tool is generated.

Finding mistakes during this phase of the process saves time and effort down the line. The approach is to rely on Machine Translation tools, and it aims at exploiting the competitive advantages humans and machines have. Humans should focus on what they do best (i.e. finding the best meaningful translation) and machines should take care of the repetitive tasks.

The SHARE team incorporated automatic checks for the translations and asked CentERdata to develop sanity checks in the TMT and to program an interface that allows the translation manager to use them for specific language and to get the outcome of the sanity check in a structured way. The sanity checks developed are the empty text field check, the missing identification number check, the missing technical text check and the fill usage check.

The team also decided to develop an Automated Verification Tool (AVT) that is able to compare the source and the target text and to assign a translation score to the text using the predictions made by a model. SHARE used the sanity checks and the AVT during the development of the national version of the SHARE wave 8 COVID CATI questionnaires.² The first for all country-specific languages while the latter only for the German questionnaire (DE, AT, CH, LU).

The innovation in the translation verification process makes the process more efficient in terms of effort and time. On one hand, sanity checks reduce the number of iterations in generating the national versions of the questionnaire tool. On the other hand, the preliminary results from the AVT provided mixed evidence about its contribution in improving the efficiency of the verification. The AVT worked technically fine. The translators easily understood the procedure. The performance of the tool mainly depended on

² Due to the current pandemic, SHARE wave 9 has been postponed and the development of the SHARE wave 8 COVID CATI took place.

the model trained. The results show a false positive rate of 72,9% for the flagged items. Translations made by native speakers, response options and short sentences had the higher false positive rates.

Overall, the SHARE team evaluates the innovation positively and it is committed to invest further in the development of the sanity checks and of the AVT.

2. Verification tools

2.1. Sanity checks

Sanity checks allow the translators to rely on machine help in checking the accuracy of the target text with respect to the programming syntax.³ Within the TMT, it is possible to access a specific interface and perform the sanity checks. Figure 1 shows the interface where it is possible to select one of the following checks:

- **Check for empty fields:** the check searches for empty text fields in the target questionnaire. It is also possible to select a subset of items to be checked. This check helps to find issues that usually do not trigger the stop of generating the new version because the process replaces the empty field with the source text.
- **Check for incorrect index:** the check searches for a missing number in front of a response option. The response options are enumerated to allow the respondent to mention the number without reading the response option to ensure privacy (e.g. list of diseases). Either not having the number or having a different one affect the data collection negatively.
- **Check Quest Logic** – the check performs an internal check of the logic in the syntax of the program that manages the questionnaire (e.g. programming syntax always ends with a semicolon “;”)
- **Check Technical texts** – the check looks for a correspondence between the source text made only with programming syntax (i.e. contains only fills) and the target text. This check also shows any empty items or misspelled instances.
- **Check Fill usage** – the check finds if source texts have fills and the target texts use no fills at all. Sometimes translators do not need gender specific fills. The aim is to find instances where translators have not used fills at all.

³ For instance, the syntax “*^FL_SinceC;*” in the sentence “*^FL_SinceC; have you or anyone...*” will deliver two sentences “*Since your last interview, have you or anyone...* and “*Since July 2020, have you or anyone...*” based on the participation of the respondent in the last interview.

Once the checks are selected; the search is activated by clicking on the button “Next”. Then, the results are displayed, and the translation manager is able to export in Excel. See Figure 2.

Challenge and lessons learnt:

- The complexity and heterogeneity of the programming syntax does not allow for an easy solution in defining the sanity checks (one-size-fit-all approach). The decision to have a flexible interface allows for the tailoring of the sanity checks to a variety of programming syntax. Further development of the checks will also ensure their output being classified correctly with respect to the questionnaire or the country-specific language (e.g. empty field is allowed for a given country for a given item).

Questionnaire Sanity check

This tool lets you check certain aspects of one or multiple translations within a questionnaire. The first check searches for empty, untranslated fields. The second check searches for response options where the index is not the same as the source text index. You can run either one or both checks. For the empty fields check, you can choose which item types you want to check.

Questionnaire/translation(s) *

SHAREw9 Corona

SOURCE - English (Generic)

German (Austria)

German (Germany)

Swedish (Sweden)

Check for empty fields

Element types

Questions

Answers

Procedures/fills

Labels

Check for incorrect index

Check Quest logic

Check Technical texts

Check Fill usage

FIGURE 1: Sanity checks selection

Questionnaire Sanity check

This tool lets you check certain aspects of one or multiple translations within a questionnaire. The first check searches for empty, untranslated fields. The second check searches for response options where the index is not the same as the source text index. You can run either one or both checks. For the empty fields check, you can choose which item types you want to check.

Check for empty fields

Questions

Nothing to report

Answers

Nothing to report

Procedures

Nothing to report

Labels

Nothing to report

FIGURE 2: Sanity checks output

2.2. Automated Verification Tool (AVT)

The process of translation verification in SHARE takes a third of the time allocated to translation procedures and it costs a person-month for each of the 28 SHARE country teams. The SHARE team's aim is to preserve high standards and to reduce the operational costs.

The SHARE team developed a tool to make the process more efficient. Unfortunately, creating machine translation systems requires large parallel corpora, which are expensive to get and/or are not available for some languages and specific domains.⁴ Therefore, the SHARE team opted to train a word-to-word translation system in an unsupervised manner, i.e., using a machine learning algorithm that analyses and clusters an unlabelled corpus. The algorithm discovers hidden patterns in the corpus without the need for human intervention (hence, it is “unsupervised”).

The SHARE team trained unsupervised bilingual word embeddings using monolingual corpora. The corpus is made of general text (Europarl) and domain specific text (survey questions).⁵ The training activities map each word of the monolingual corpus into a vector of real numbers.

Once the bilingual word embeddings model has been trained and tested, the SHARE team developed the AVT in order to check translations. These are the main steps handled by the tool.

1) The AVT imports the questions and, using the trained model, it generates the 10 best foreign language translations of each English word.⁶ If one of the best translations is in the human foreign language translation, 3) the AVT marks the word pair as matched. By measuring the number of matched word pairs, 4) the AVT estimates the translation quality. As a last step, 5) the AVT stores the translation quality scores and reports them to the user. The translation score is given by the ratio of the number of matched words and the number of the words in the target text. The steps 1-5 are programmed in Python. Milestone M18 provides more details about the AVT.⁷ The AVT tool is available at the following GitHub repository⁸.

⁴ A text corpus (plural corpora) is a language resource consisting of a large and structured set of texts. A parallel corpus is a collection of texts, each of which is translated into one or more other languages than the original.

⁵ Europarl: A Parallel Corpus for Statistical Machine Translation, Philipp Koehn, MT Summit 2005

⁶ This step is also called bilingual lexicon induction where word translations are induced from monolingual corpora in two languages.

⁷ Yuri Pettinicchi. (2021). MS18 Beta version of automatic verification software available for testing (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681310>

⁸ AVT tool in GitHub: https://github.com/yichennliu/bwes_translation (accessed Oct 2021)

Challenges and lesson learnt:

- In order to improve the performance of the model, the team collected a new set of training data, the domain specific text from the MCSQ version 1.1 (Beatrice Worsley) developed by ESS/UPF in SSHOC Task 4.2. “Preparing tools for the use of Computer Assisted Translation”).
- The SHARE team used the Vecmap⁹ (cross-lingual word embedding mappings) to create models on different sizes of training data. The performance did not improve beyond a given threshold even with larger training data. The team decided to try a different approach than collecting more training data. The next project aims at training phrase based or sentence based embeddings.

3. SHARE Exercise

3.1. The questionnaire

In June 2020, SHARE started the fieldwork of a new “SHARE Corona Survey”. A sub-sample of SHARE’s panel respondents was interviewed via a Computer Assisted Telephone Interview (CATI) to collect data on the same topics as in the regular SHARE questionnaire - but shortened and targeted to the COVID-19 living situation of people who are 50 years and older. The data collected allowed examining in-depth how the risk group of the older individuals was coping with the health-related and socioeconomic impact of COVID-19. The great advantage of these data was the possibility to measure and interpret differences in a cross-country and a longitudinal dimension.

The questionnaire is named SHARE wave 8 COVID CATI. It covers the most important life domains for the target population and asks specific questions about infections and changes in life during the lockdown:

- **Health and health behaviour:** General health before and after the COVID-19 outbreak, practice of safety measures (e.g. social distancing, wearing a mask).
- **Mental health:** Anxiety, depression, sleeping problems, and loneliness before and after the COVID-19 outbreak.
- **Infections and healthcare:** COVID-19 related symptoms, SARS-CoV-2 testing and hospitalization, forgone medical treatment, satisfaction with treatments.

⁹ See <https://github.com/artetxem/vecmap> for programming codes. For details, Mikel Artetxe, Gorka Labaka, and Eneko Agirre. 2018. A robust self-learning method for fully unsupervised cross-lingual mappings of word embeddings. In Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers).

- **Changes in work and economic situation:** Unemployment, business closures, working from home, changes in working hours and income, financial support.
- **Social networks:** Changes in personal contacts with family and friends, help given and received, personal care given and received.

More specifically, the questionnaire accounts for 242 text items classified as question text (128), interviewer’s instruction (29) and response option (85). The total number of words in the source text is 11080.

3.2. Workflow

The verification exercise is a two-step procedure, and it starts after translators have provided the target text. The output under verification is the parallel corpora made by source text and target text of the questionnaire. The two steps are: 1) verifying with sanity checks and 2) verifying with the AVT.

First, the translation manager performs the sanity checks directly in the TMT. The items that do not pass the checks are flagged as “Check Failed” in the TMT and, only for those, the translators take actions. Then, the translation manager performs another round of sanity checks on the new version of the parallel corpora and terminates the first part of the verification phase as soon as there are no more items flagged as “Checked Failed”.

In the second step, the translation manager exports the parallel corpora out of the TMT and imports it in the Automated Translation Tool that provides the translation score for each pair of source-target text. Then, the translation managers flags as “Check Failed” the items for which the score is below a given threshold and, only for those, the translators take actions, reviewing the target text.

Figure 3 describes the workflow. The steps are:

- 1) The source text is sent to the translators.
- 2) The target text is produced, and the parallel corpora created.
- 3) Sanity checks are performed on the current version of the parallel corpora.
- 4) The items can be flagged as “Check ok” or “Check Failed”.
- 5) Translators take care of the “Check Failed” items.
- 6) Translators provide a new version of the target text.
- 7) Sanity checks are performed on the current version of the parallel corpora.
 - a. If one item is flagged “Checked Failed”, then it goes through 4-7.
- 8) When all items are flagged as “Check OK”, ...

- 9) ... the parallel corpora is imported in the AVT.
- 10) Once all the items are flagged as “Checked Ok”, the national questionnaire can be exported for the generation of the national version of the questionnaire tool.

FIGURE 3: WORKFLOW

4. Results

The verification exercise made use of the sanity checks for all the 39 country-specific languages available in SHARE. Table 1 shows the details of the translation process, such as languages and working time.

The performance of the translation verification exercise is related to the degree of complexity of the source text, the ability of the translators to work in the TMT environment and the time available to perform the translation task. The ideal scenario to evaluate the innovation in the translation verification is to set up an experiment where only single aspects are altered at the time. The SHARE team had to make use of the innovation under special circumstances (i.e. the onset of the COVID pandemic) that halted the development of the SHARE wave 9 and pushed the SHARE team to develop the SHARE wave 8 COVID CATI questionnaire described in section 3.1.

The results rely on the effective fieldwork experience. Table 1 reports the languages checked the number of days between the end of the translation phase and the generation of the last national version of the questionnaire tool, and the number of national versions generated.

The SHARE exercise shows that it took 24 days, on average, from the time the translators ended the translation phase to the time the last national version of the questionnaire tool was generated. It also shows that between three and four national versions per country-specific language were generated in that span of time.

These results suggest an increase in the efficiency of the translation procedures. Previous SHARE waves took at least two months and more than four iterations during the development phase of the national versions of the questionnaire tool. A word of caveat is due here. The SHARE wave 8 COVID CATI was developed using new software and the source text has a lower amount of programming syntax than the standard SHARE questionnaire.

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW NATIONAL VERSION SHARE WAVE 8 COVID CATI

	COUNTRY	LANGUAGE	End of the translation phase	Last Version generated	Days	Iterations
1	Austria	<i>German</i>	30/04/2020	08/06/2020	39	5
2	Belgium	<i>French</i>	01/05/2020	29/05/2020	28	3
3	Belgium	<i>Flemish</i>	11/05/2020	28/05/2020	17	3
4	Bulgaria	<i>Bulgarian</i>	04/05/2020	08/05/2020	4	2
5	Croatia	<i>Croatian</i>	04/05/2020	01/06/2020	28	3
6	Cyprus	<i>Greek</i>	30/04/2020	13/05/2020	13	3
7	Czech Republic	<i>Czech</i>	04/05/2020	01/06/2020	28	4
8	Denmark	<i>Danish</i>	01/05/2020	29/05/2020	28	3
9	Estonia	<i>Estonian</i>	07/05/2020	02/06/2020	26	4
10		<i>Russian</i>	07/05/2020	02/06/2020	26	4
11	Finland	<i>Finnish</i>	08/05/2020	02/06/2020	25	4
12		<i>Swedish</i>	13/05/2020	04/06/2020	22	5
13	France	<i>French</i>	30/04/2020	02/06/2020	33	4
14	Germany	<i>German</i>	30/04/2020	02/06/2020	33	5
15	Greece	<i>Greek</i>	04/05/2020	29/05/2020	25	3
16	Hungary	<i>Hungarian</i>	06/05/2020	03/06/2020	28	4
17		<i>Arabic</i>	05/05/2020	01/06/2020	27	3
18		<i>Hebrew</i>	05/05/2020	01/06/2020	27	4
19	Israel	<i>Russian</i>	05/05/2020	01/06/2020	27	4
20		<i>Italian</i>	04/05/2020	29/05/2020	25	3
21	Latvia	<i>Latvian</i>	07/05/2020	01/06/2020	25	3
22		<i>Russian</i>	08/05/2020	01/06/2020	24	3
23	Lithuania	<i>Lithuanian</i>	07/05/2020	01/06/2020	25	3
24	Luxembourg	<i>French</i>	30/04/2020	11/05/2020	11	2
25		<i>German</i>	06/05/2020	14/05/2020	8	2
26	Malta	<i>Maltese</i>	07/05/2020	29/05/2020	22	3
27		<i>English</i>	07/05/2020	13/05/2020	6	2
28	Netherlands	<i>Dutch</i>	01/05/2020	12/05/2020	11	2
29	Poland	<i>Polish</i>	12/05/2020	14/05/2020	2	2
30	Portugal	<i>Portuguese</i>	30/04/2020	01/06/2020	32	5
31	Romania	<i>Romanian</i>	05/05/2020	03/06/2020	29	3
32	Slovakia	<i>Slovak</i>	04/05/2020	29/05/2020	25	4
33	Slovenia	<i>Slovenian</i>	01/05/2020	03/06/2020	33	3
34	Spain	<i>Spanish</i>	01/05/2020	05/06/2020	35	5
35	Spain-Girona	<i>Catalan</i>	30/04/2020	01/06/2020	32	3
36	Sweden	<i>Swedish</i>	01/05/2020	04/06/2020	34	4
37	Switzerland	<i>German</i>	05/05/2020	04/06/2020	30	5
38		<i>French</i>	05/05/2020	04/06/2020	30	5
39		<i>Italian</i>	05/05/2020	04/06/2020	30	5
				Average	24.44	3.51

The verification exercise made use also of the AVT for the four German country-specific languages (DE, AT, CH, LU). The items verified amount to 968 (242*4). Figure 4 shows the distribution of the translation score when all the items are pooled together. On average, 60% of the words has been matched (translation score: mean 0.59 – st. dev. 0.28). This result is similar to the one observed during the testing of the model.

FIGURE 4: Distribution of the translation score

The red line indicates the threshold (45%) below which the item is flagged. Given this threshold, 255 items (26.3% of the total) were flagged and reviewed by translators. The feedback from the translators was measured as “action needed” or “no action needed”. The former case applied to 69 items, and it implies a true positive rate lower than 30% (i.e. 27,1% of the flagged ones needed some action). The latter case applied to the other 186 items leading to a false positive rate of 72,9%.

In order to identify for which items the tool works better, the results are reported per country teams, per types of item and per text length. Table 2 reports the results per country team. Luxembourg drove most of the effect with the lowest average translation score (0.55) and the highest number of flagged items (78). The false positive rate for Luxembourg is 28% while it is above 80% for the other countries where the verification did not substantially help in improving the quality of final translation. This result suggests that the performance of the tool depends also on the quality of the translation.

TABLE 2. FLAGGED ITEMS BY COUNTRY

	Austria	Germany	Luxembourg	Switzerland
N	242	242	242	242
Translation Score	.593 (.285)	.612 (.286)	.559 (.285)	.594 (.281)
Flagged Items	58 (24%)	59 (24%)	78 (32%)	60 (25%)
Outcome	0 (0%) 58 (100%)	4 (6%) 55 (94%)	56 (72%) 22 (28%)	9 (15%) 51 (85%)

Table 3 reports the results by type of text. Interviewers' instruction has the lowest average translation score (0.47) and the highest number of flagged items in percentage (47%). The false positive rate is lower for question text and interviewers' instruction than for response options. This result suggests that the tool easily misreports when the length of the text is shorter (i.e. response options are usually made by few words).

TABLE 3: FLAGGED ITEMS BY TYPE OF TEXT

	Qtext	Qinstruction	Response Option
N	512	116	340
Translation Score	.61 (.230)	.470 (.201)	.59 (.362)
Flagged Items	82 (16%)	55 (47%)	118 (35%)
Outcome	28 (34%) 54 (66%)	17 (31%) 38 (69%)	24 (20%) 94 (80%)

Table 4 reports the results by the length of the text. The length is computed by the number of words; less than three words, between four and ten, between eleven and twenty and more than twenty. Shorter texts display a higher rate of flagged items. However, longer texts display higher true positive rate, as expected. When text is short, one matched word more substantially affects the translation score, lowering the robustness of the tool. Moreover, this result suggests that long texts have a higher degree of complexity that the tool is not able to address properly.

TABLE 4: FLAGGED ITEMS BY THE LENGTH OF THE TEXT

#words	1-3	4-10	11-20	20+
N	318	242	254	154
Translation Score	.633 (.397)	.548 (.277)	.588 (.153)	.567 (.132)
Flagged Items	92 (29%)	92 (38%)	44 (17%)	27 (17%)
Outcome	23 (25%) 69 (75%)	21 (22%) 71 (78%)	13 (29%) 31 (71%)	12 (44%) 15 (56%)

5. Conclusion

From the verification exercise, the SHARE team learnt that the innovation described makes the process more efficient in terms of effort and time. Sanity checks reduce the number of iterations in generating the national versions of the questionnaire tool. The preliminary results from the Automated Verification tool (AVT) provided mixed evidence about its contribution in improving the efficiency of the verification.

The AVT worked technically fine. Also, the procedure was easily understood by the translators and smoothly implemented. The performance mainly depends on the model trained. The false positive rate for the flagged items is 72,9%. Translations made by native speakers, response options and short sentences had the higher false positive rates.

One possible explanation is the absence of certain words in the training dataset, e.g., Coronavirus, COVID. A way to improve the tool is to retrain the model adding these words to the monolingual corpora. Also, the training of bilingual phrase embeddings model is another way to improve the performance of the tool. The SHARE team will pursue these steps in future projects.

6. References

- Artetxe M., Labaka G., and Agirre E. (2018) *A robust self-learning method for fully unsupervised cross-lingual mappings of word embeddings*. In Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)
- Koehn P. (2005) *Europarl: A Parallel Corpus for Statistical Machine Translation*, MT Summit 2005
- Martens, M. (2017) *Uploaded and modularized TMT*. Deliverable 3.12 of the SERISS project funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme GA No: 654221.
- Pettinicchi, Y. (2021). *MS18 Beta version of automatic verification software available for testing (v1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681310>